

INTEGRATION BETWEEN BASIC EDUCATION AND INDUSTRY: REFLECTIONS AND RESULTS OF UNIVERSITY EXTENSION IN INDUSTRIAL EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

The extension project titled “Industrial Awakening” aimed to bridge the gap between high school graduates and industries in the electromechanical sector in the municipality of Passo Fundo, Rio Grande do Sul. The industrial sector has suffered significantly from a shortage of skilled labor, evidenced by the large number of hard-to-fill job openings in the region. Furthermore, there is a misconception regarding the industrial environment, with the belief that it does not offer good opportunities for personal and professional growth and is an environment that hinders creativity or innovation. To address this issue, training seminars on soft and hard skills were organized, along with visits to partner industries, to familiarize students with the production process and activities across various sectors, thereby sparking interest in careers within the field of materials production and processing. Finally, the extension project created a link between industry, academia, and schools, fostering significant development in the public speaking, metrology, and emotional intelligence skills of the students involved. Additionally, it was observed that some participants identified with the sector, expressing interest in professional training and future employment.

KEYWORDS

University Extension; Industrial Education; Industrial Career; Professional Development; Industry 4.0.

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INTRODUCTION

Ranked as the largest city in the northern part of the state of Rio Grande do Sul, Passo Fundo has a diverse industrial base, with the electromechanical sector being one of the most important for the economy of the “Capital of the Planalto Médio” (AGRONEGÓCIO, 2024). This segment plays an indispensable role in the production and processing of materials, as it is a foundational sector, supplying goods, machinery, and equipment to the entire market (SEBRAE, 2012). In this context, the region stands out for its high demand for parts and implements related to agribusiness. The municipality ranks 6th among the state’s largest economies (ECONOMIA, 2024), with industry being one of the sectors that generates the most jobs, accounting for nearly 11,000 positions. However, a net loss of 171 jobs was observed in September 2024 (CAGED, 2024). This fact underscores the difficulty in finding skilled professionals or young people interested in the service sector.

With the advent of globalization, previously nonexistent professions have emerged, multiplying job options. Consequently, regional economic growth has led to a shortage of skilled labor. The vast majority of high school graduates end up choosing to enter the job market in the technology and services sectors, rather than in industry. On the other hand, the Fourth Industrial Revolution, or Industry 4.0, introduces a new form of production that uses digital technologies for automation and data exchange, making processes more efficient and productive. However, employees are held to higher standards regarding the qualifications needed to perform their duties in the face of new production technologies. Consequently, those who demonstrate interest and aptitude for the respective roles are recruited, with the aim of developing their skills later. According to Vendruscolo (2023), approximately 10% of job openings remain unfilled at all levels of the industrial sector in the region.

In basic education, students are aware of the importance of a diploma, but in many cases have not learned the value of knowledge for launching a professional career. However, there is sometimes a diminished interest in understanding the application of the concepts studied. According to Barros et al. (2012), there are difficulties related to the receptiveness, availability, and inflexibility of some high school teachers in implementing more engaging learning methodologies. Furthermore, the national education model is not aligned with current needs, and the lack of infrastructure in schools ends up being yet another impediment to carrying out certain activities. Therefore, it is evident within classrooms that there is a significant lack of encouragement for professional development, which can make entering the job market more difficult.

To minimize this problem, the high school curriculum needs to be updated to explore the interactions between the education sector and industry, thereby bringing students closer to the realities of the professional world. In short, it is necessary to offer students practical and tangible opportunities to explore the theoretical concepts they have learned, sparking their interest, giving new meaning to their learning, and enabling them to apply it to real-world problems in everyday industrial settings. As a result, understanding the factory work environment will reveal different processes and technologies related to various professions, opening up perspectives for future careers and leading students to consider industry as a viable option.

Bringing engineering education closer to the real-world problems of industry is essential to ensure that future professionals are prepared to face the challenges of the job market and meet the needs and demands of companies. When students are exposed to real-world industry problems during their academic training, they have the opportunity to apply what they learn in practical situations, which can help them develop skills and knowledge useful in the real world. Furthermore, this approach can help make academic training more relevant and up-to-date, fostering valuable employment opportunities and partnerships, given that the industry is constantly evolving.

In light of the above, this extension project, developed by the Quadruple Helix (higher education institutions, industry, civil society, and the Government of the State of Rio Grande do Sul), aimed to spark interest in industrial careers by introducing high school seniors to the challenges of the electromechanical sector, with support from extension students in the engineering undergraduate programs at Atitus Educação, in the municipality of Passo Fundo, Rio Grande do Sul.

OBJECTIVES

General Objective

To spark the interest of adolescents and young people in industrial and technological activities, creating career opportunities and access to decent work, while promoting economic growth.

Specific Objectives

To increase the interest of young people and adolescents in job opportunities in local industry;
Provide quality training to young people and adolescents, opening up new possibilities for the future;

Align academic training with the real needs of the electromechanical industry.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The manufacturing industry has been facing the growing challenge of a shortage of skilled labor in recent years. The shortage of professionals with specific technical knowledge is a concern for the business community and may delay economic recovery (CIDADÃ, 2022). According to a survey conducted by ManpowerGroup, in 2023, a total of 80% of employers had difficulty hiring professionals to fill vacancies, ranging from the simplest positions to those requiring greater preparation and training. Faced with this challenge, employers have come to understand the need to support their employees' learning and invest in staff development (MANPOWERGROUP, 2023).

All of these observed challenges are also the result of an intense process of change driven by technological advancement and development—that is, by the advent of Industry 4.0. As new production and automation processes are being integrated into the industrial context, new jobs are emerging and requiring compatible technical skills, known as *Hard Skills*. On the other hand, competencies such as communication, leadership, problem-solving, and teamwork are essential to ensuring efficiency and productivity in operations (SENAI, 2022). These interpersonal skills are called *Soft Skills* and play a role just as important as technical knowledge. For this reason, managers have recognized this and changed the selection process, evaluating interest, aptitude, and other requirements in order to invest in the employee after hiring.

In recent years, the number of young people interested in building a career in the industrial sector has dropped significantly. Furthermore, many of them perceive the industry as a monotonous work environment with few opportunities for innovation and creativity, offering limited social and financial mobility. While it is true that some careers may offer lower salaries compared to other fields, many also provide opportunities for professional and financial growth. In this context, according to Purcenoa et al. (2016), it is essential that young graduates avoid complacency or stagnation by following the three key stages of a career: career choice, competition for the desired position, and career advancement.

According to data from the IBGE, one in five Brazilians between the ages of 15 and 29 was neither studying nor employed in 2022. Furthermore, the 2023 School Census, released by the Ministry of Education (MEC), indicated that 5.9% of enrolled students dropped out of high school in 2023.

These data highlight the lack of teaching methodologies that are more engaging and relevant to professional life. Furthermore, a topic of great interest among students relates to professional vocation (BAZZO, M. G.; CASTRO, C. O., 2018). Given this, it is clear that a new approach, combined with a humanized educational methodology and interactions between the education sector and industry—thereby bringing students closer to professional reality—would contribute positively to a more attractive and efficient education.

METHODOLOGY

The extension project sought to develop a solid partnership between industries in the electromechanical sector, high schools, and the undergraduate programs in Mechanical Engineering, Electrical Engineering, and Production Engineering at ATITUS Educação. To this end, technical subjects and specific topics to be covered were defined, such as: metrology, communication, behavior, reading blueprints, systems thinking, and the Microsoft Office suite, among others. In this way, it was possible to provide an early experience of the reality of the job market, in order to integrate, raise awareness, train, and foster a desire to learn, with the goal of sparking interest in careers in the field of materials production and processing.

Selection of extension workers and visits to industries

At the beginning of the second semester of 2023, approximately 250 high school seniors were approached, of whom only 8 participated in the outreach project. During the activities, students had the opportunity to visit partner industries in the electromechanical sector, such as Fertisystem, Ezata Industrial, ADG Plásticos, and Automasul. These visits provided a deeper understanding of production processes, ranging from the assembly line to logistics. Students were able to observe, in practice, how each industry operates and how theoretical concepts apply to the industrial environment.

Metrology Classes

The topic of metrology was an important part of the extension program. Students learned about measuring instruments, including calipers. They also practiced using these instruments by measuring parts provided by one of the project's partner industries, comparing the measurements with the specified tolerances. This process allowed them to acquire practical skills essential for taking precise measurements of parts, preparing them to apply this knowledge effectively in real-world situations.

Figure 1 - Practical metrology class.

Source: Authors (2024).

Mentoring and Project Development

Mentoring sessions were also held, during which students received guidance from experienced professionals. Additionally, they worked on developing projects and seminars, which helped improve their communication and teamwork skills. Among these activities, the workshop “Human Relations: Why Is This Important?” stood out. It was conducted by SEBRAE (Brazilian Micro and Small Business Support Service) and focused on emotional intelligence and interpersonal relationships in the workplace. Students and scholarship recipients were encouraged to participate in various exercises focused on their personality and communication skills, with the aim of improving their ability to build and maintain social relationships in the workplace.

Figure 2 – Workshop seminar “Human Relations: Why Is This Important?”.

Source: Authors (2024).

Figure 3 – Seminar presented by extension students.

Source: Authors (2024).

Basic Word and Excel Skills

To improve productivity and written communication, students received training in the basics of Word and Excel. They learned how to create tables and histograms, format documents, and write articles. These skills are valuable in both academic and professional settings.

Figure 4 – Hands-on Word and Excel class.

Source: Authors (2024).

Introduction to the Arduino system

Finally, students had the opportunity to explore the world of programming and automation through the Arduino system. They learned to write code, connect sensors and actuators, and develop simple projects on Arduino. Additionally, they had the opportunity to observe and understand how multimeters work. This hands-on experience in programming and automation is essential not only for future engineers and computer scientists but also for anyone wishing to apply this knowledge in various areas of life.

RESULTS/DISCUSSION

After completing all the stages involved in the project, it was observed that, of the eight students initially enrolled, only three completed the program. Furthermore, it was evident that the students developed a certain degree of awareness regarding industrial careers, coming to view them as dignified work.

Certain challenges faced by the extension workers were also identified, related to the drafting and writing of articles, as well as hesitation regarding the presentation of the conclusions and insights from their experiences.

Furthermore, for graduates of ATITUS's engineering programs, early exposure to the job market enabled them to identify the main demands of the industrial sector, fostering an education focused on minimizing the shortcomings of academic training and strengthening the start of their professional careers.

IMPLICATIONS

The project's implications are significant on several levels. In the educational field, the results indicate the need for curricular reforms, with greater emphasis on practices and methodologies that connect technical education to the real demands of the job market, promoting a more practical and up-to-date education. In the economic sphere, the project suggests a positive impact on participants' employability by equipping them with specific and transferable skills required by industry, thereby strengthening the link between academia and the productive sector. Furthermore, the project's success may influence public policies aimed at expanding university extension initiatives, particularly in areas of technological innovation and regional development, thereby promoting social and economic inclusion. Finally, the potential for replicating and expanding similar projects stands out, broadening the reach and benefits to other communities and regions in need of skilled labor.

CONTRIBUTIONS

The results obtained include a significant increase in students' practical and theoretical knowledge, both regarding the industrial environment and knowledge of certain content

necessary for professional practice. In addition, there was an improvement in communication and teamwork skills, as well as a deeper understanding of the labor market and industries, facilitated by the technical visits and practical activities conducted.

For the school environment, the project proposal serves as a reinforcement of the current education system, particularly at the high school level, contributing to the enrichment of educational quality within technology-focused training tracks and the development of *soft* and *hard skills*.

Finally, for the industrial sector, the enhancement of perceptions regarding job positions at all levels, through the integration of basic education and industry, may result in an increase in the number of applicants for positions that remain open, thereby helping to alleviate the labor shortage.

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